

theory of harmful individual choices that provide permanence and development of problems in humanity

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Summary: the theory presents a statement and explanation that countless problems in humanity originate from individual choice, in addition, the persistence of problems in humanity is also motivated by individual choice. It is possible to observe the theory through knowledge of the history of humanity where individual action resulted in the origin and permanence of problems in humanity. It is worth mentioning that negative choices are not based on information even though it exists, meanwhile, positive choices are guided by coherent and detailed information generating positive results. In general, when you have coherent information and it is not used in this way, you tend to develop impairment due to choice.

Keyword: loss by choice. Problems in humanity. Source of problems. problems persist.

Introduction

There are numerous observable historical and current cases that problems in humanity such as social and economic problem can be driven by individual choice, developing the theory of harm by choice. The idea of harm by choice can be understood by obtaining information inherent to politicians where they often make decisions based on pure opinion affecting society in a negative way. When there is coherent and detailed information regarding a problem, negative opinions are unnecessary, given that information can guide the decision. Furthermore, there are those individuals who have the power to influence (other than politicians), but influence on a negative side.

In general, the theory presents a statement that individual choices can make humanity unable to solve problems, in addition to developing new problems in humanity. Furthermore, it is worth highlighting that the decision to leave essential individual choices to solve a problem absent is also a choice, that is, there are cases of an individual decision to remain absent in the face of problems.

Although some politicians present their application ideas to voters at the time of the election, not all ideas are actually presented, that is, in occasional cases politicians need to make decisions based on the occasional moment, that is, new decisions are unknown to voters until election time.

Therefore, the theory can be understood as the initial problem of many other problems in humanity in addition to remaining in the problems. There are cases where not even accessible and detailed information is capable of changing harmful individual choices.

Problems in humanity in relation to theory

A problem in humanity is a situation of high losses for a huge portion of society and has harmful effects on the development of humanity, such as violence, hunger, unemployment, lack of access to quality healthcare, social inequalities, prejudice and climate change.

These problems must be eliminated, given the serious damage to the human condition. These problems of humanity exist due to numerous factors such as economic, government, cultural and historical. However, these factors are possible due to the theory of prejudice by choice that configures the origin and permanence of all these factors that generate these problems in humanity.

An example of a social problem: social inequality

Social inequality is a problem that occurs when a specific number of people have access to more resources and opportunities than other people. Social inequality can be caused by several factors, such as discrimination, social exclusion, economic, political and historical systems, among others. This social problem contributes to the emergence of a series of other social problems, such as:

1. Unequal access to education;
2. Health disparity;
3. Unemployment due to lack of opportunities;
4. Marginalization of social groups;
5. High number of people living on the streets;
6. High cases of violence in the city.

It is necessary to detail the factors that cause social inequality:

Prejudice: prejudice based on characteristics such as religion, ethnicity, gender or sexual orientation can limit access to opportunities and resources for certain groups, contributing to social inequality.

Income Distribution: The way income and opportunities are distributed in society plays an important role in the development of social inequalities. The lack of access to well-paid jobs, quality education and economic opportunities can encourage social inequality.

Political and Economic Organizations: Government policy, economic structures, and taxation systems play an essential role in determining the distribution of resources. Economic models that favor certain groups, that is, do not favor society as a whole, provide wealth concentration, thereby increasing social inequality.

Historical inheritance: The transmission of wealth and privileges from generation to generation can result in specific groups having significant advantages compared to others. The lack of social mobility, where it is difficult for people to develop their socioeconomic position economically, also

contributes to the problem of social inequality.

Education and equal opportunities: Differences in the quality of education can lead to significant differences in life opportunities. Lack of access to quality education can limit employment prospects and cycles of poverty persist.

Globalization: although globalization has provided economic benefits in numerous cases, it can also contribute to inequality, as not all groups or regions benefit equally from global economic changes.

Historical Conditions: The history of a country or region often leaves a legacy that affects current social and economic structures for future generations, and can contribute to persistent inequalities.

Social inequality statistics

The Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) released data from the Gini index of per capita household income, an indicator of inequality, which shows a drop from 0.544 in 2021 to 0.518 in 2022. The number was also below that of 2019, when it was 0.544. The Gini Index measures the concentration of income distribution and the closer it is to 1, the greater the inequality. And the closer to zero, the smaller the inequality. Among the poorest 5%, the average monthly income per capita was R\$87 in 2022. This value represents an increase of 102.3% compared to R\$43 in 2021. In the next range, between the 5% and the 10% with the lowest income, the increase was 47.5%, to R\$ 239. The group of those with income between 10% and 20% poorest, in turn, had an increase of 22.7%, to R \$378.

Among the population with greater economic power, in the group between the richest 95% and 99%, the increase in income was 0.5%, to R\$6,882. In the range between 90% and 95% richest, growth was 5.8%, to R\$3,901. In the group between 80% and 90% with higher incomes, there was an increase of 7.4%, to R\$2,521.

Furthermore, other data from civil society organizations launched the Brazilian Observatory of Inequality says that currently, the 0.01% that make up the richest population in Brazil, have an accumulated and debt-free fortune of R\$151 million on average. The average monthly per capita income of the richest 10% is also 14.4 times greater than that of the poorest 40%. On the other hand, more than 7.5 million people live with a per capita household income of less than R\$150 per month. The report also reinforces that those who earn less pay more taxes in Brazil. "The poorest 10% pay 26.4% of their income in taxes, while the richest 10% pay only 19.2%", states the text. Women and black people are those who suffer the most from the impacts of inequality and also those who have the least political representation, in the executive, legislative and judiciary.

These data demonstrate the reality of social inequality still present in humanity today.

Historical case of social inequality

Source: prepared by the author. figure 1
Caption: the influence relationships of choice.

With the beginning of Portuguese colonization, there was a need to find cheap labor to produce wealth. Enslaving native peoples was the solution, starting intense social inequality. In addition to a decimation of the native population.

Not satisfied with the results presented, it was necessary to find cheap labor that would provide quick and abundant profits. The Portuguese quickly began to ethnocentrically disqualify them as culturally inferior, indolent and lazy. To this day, they suffer from cultural marginalization, the result of this disqualification, in addition to being left with the stigma of 'vagabonds', all of this, has enabled a culture of social exclusion, developing social inequality.

With the end of native slavery, Africans came, another group that suffered and still suffers from social inequality due to intense exploitation, slavery caused losses from generation to generation. Upon arriving in Brazil, they were forced to assume dominant cultural values, that is, they were forcibly acculturated and forced to learn language, customs, religion, cultural values, in addition to providing wealth for the large landowners.

Even with the end of slavery, the situation of former slaves did not change and, to this day, they remain culturally marginalized and poor due to colonization that did not allow education and land to enslaved groups. Currently there are government measures to make harmful corrections caused by the past of slavery, such as quotas. These measures are part of so-called affirmative actions, which aim to reduce the enormous inequality between blacks and whites. The need for these correction measures is clear as the information guides this practice.

Colonization decisions were largely motivated by the interests of the Portuguese crown, especially during the reign of Dom João, therefore, Dom João had the power to influence colonization decisions, the absence or presence of Dom João's choices made colonization possible .

Historical case of Nazism

Source: prepared by the author. figure 2
Caption: the influence relationships of choice.

Nazism was an extreme right-wing ideology that emerged in Germany in the 1920s and manifested itself through the National Socialist German Workers' Party. He became known for defending extreme nationalism, with anti-Semitic, anti-democracy, militaristic, openly racist ideas, among others. The party leader was the Austrian Adolf Hitler, known for his great cruelty. Hitler took power from Germany in 1933, upon being appointed leader, and implemented a totalitarian dictatorship that persecuted and killed opponents, in addition to preparing the country for war, causing serious damage to humanity such as death and financial crises. Adolf Hitler had great decision-making power over the German people. In other words, Hitler was the person who contributed in a relevant way to the racist practices and persecution of the Jews, due to his great influence Hitler could choose to end the harmful practices.

In detail, Nazism defended the superiority of the white man and eugenic ideas, that is, the possibility of a "purification of the human race". The prejudice present in Nazism also included intense anti-Semitism, prejudice towards Jewish people, very common in German society. Nazi practices influenced the existence of prejudice, causing serious damage to specific groups.
No influence on choices

An argument may arise against the theory presented when it states that choices are influenced by the context and their relative needs, that is, this argument tries to invalidate the idea that choices are the beginning of other social problems, that is, it is the context and their relative needs that promote the origin of social problems even promote choice. However, this argument has two flaws, considering that countless historical examples of humanity show that social problems arise without context and their relative needs, that is, social problems have their origin without rational support, that is, without influence on choices, such as colonization and Nazism.

An example of an applicable hypothetical case

Source: prepared by the author. figure 3
Caption: choice influence relationships

In the hypothetical case based on historical knowledge. Therefore, in the case of a political leader Furthermore, this politician, in the context of a pandemic in which the disease is killing thousands of people and in the case of an economically well-off country for purchasing vaccines, decides to deny vaccines, allowing thousands more deaths. Furthermore, politician x has access to important information of the vaccine, who, on the other hand, is frequently warned about the importance of the vaccine in combating the pandemic, yet denies the vaccine. Therefore, the only politician made possible damage in different ways, characterizing the theory of prejudice by choice. It is observed that the implications of the choice generate more damage when people have the power to influence.

Positive choice

Positive choices occur when they take coherent and detailed information into account. Thus, an ideal example of this case is the Lula government, where numerous benefits for the poorest were developed. Statistics confirm that the Lula government was positive in bringing corrections or mitigating social problems. In this sense, it is possible that a political leader's choices can generate positive results.

Conclusion

Therefore, according to explanations contained in the article, the statement that choices are capable of developing new problems in humanity is coherent. In addition, other social problems persist. It is worth mentioning that the damage is intense when dealing with people with the power to influence realities, such as political leaders. There are thousands of historical examples that reinforce the theory, such as: colonization and Nazism.

On the other hand, choices guided by coherent and detailed information about such a problem can make this choice capable of solving or mitigating problems in humanity.

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